

Supporting Information File S2

Mathematica code for: Remodeling and the Evolution of Sexual Autonomy by Mate Choice

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We extended the classic Kirkpatrick (1982) two-locus sexual selection model to include sexually coercive male behavior (c) and mutation bias at the male display trait locus (T). We analytically solve the model for the case where the female preference allele, P_2 , is equal to one. This yields an expression for stable equilibria for T_2 between zero and one that represents a balance of female preference, coercive behavior, viability selection, and biased mutation. We use this to calculate the starting frequency for T_2 in the full model.

See Table 1 for definitions of alleles and key parameters.

*Note on parametrization: in the main text and Appendices S1–S3, we refer to the mutation parameter as " u " to avoid confusion with the subscript m used to denote male genotype frequencies. In the code below, the mutation parameter is denoted " m " and has been left as such to avoid the introduction of errors.

In[]:=

```
ClearAll[genotypes, st, at, T1P1, T1P2, T2P1, T2P2,
postsel, Mating, u, z, init1, zygotes, r, LD, Trait, Pref,
Thing, T2, P2, DTP, m, sp, v, b, Teq, Teq1, Teq2, c, new, recomb]
```

```

In[ ]:= init1 = Solve[{T1P1 + T1P2 + T2P1 + T2P2 == 1, T1P2 + T2P2 == P2,
      T2P1 + T2P2 == T2, DTP == T2P2 - T2 * P2}, {T1P1, T1P2, T2P1, T2P2}];
T1P1 = T1P1 /. init1;
T1P2 = T1P2 /. init1;
T2P1 = T2P1 /. init1;
T2P2 = T2P2 /. init1;
r = 1 / 2;

new = Table[Table[i, {i, 4}], {j, 16}];
recomb = {{1, 0, 0, 0}, {1/2, 1/2, 0, 0}, {1/2, 0, 1/2, 0},
  {(1-r)/2, r/2, r/2, (1-r)/2}, {1/2, 1/2, 0, 0},
  {0, 1, 0, 0}, {r/2, (1-r)/2, (1-r)/2, r/2}, {0, 1/2, 0, 1/2},
  {1/2, 0, 1/2, 0}, {r/2, (1-r)/2, (1-r)/2, r/2},
  {0, 0, 1, 0}, {0, 0, 1/2, 1/2}, {(1-r)/2, r/2, r/2, (1-r)/2},
  {0, 1/2, 0, 1/2}, {0, 0, 1/2, 1/2}, {0, 0, 0, 1}};

genotypes = Flatten[{T1P1, T1P2, T2P1, T2P2, (T1P1 * T2P2 - T1P2 * T2P1)}];
(*the fifth element is for keeping track of LD*)

genotypes

Out[ ]:= {1 + DTP - P2 - T2 + P2 T2, -DTP + P2 - P2 T2, -DTP + T2 - P2 T2, DTP + P2 T2,
  - (-DTP + P2 - P2 T2) (-DTP + T2 - P2 T2) + (DTP + P2 T2) (1 + DTP - P2 - T2 + P2 T2) }

```

```

In[*]:= (*make a vector that will perform Natural Selection on males,
affecting gene frequencies before mating*)

postsel = Table[i, {i, 1, 4}];
u = Total[genotypes[[1 ;; 2]] + (1 - st) * Total[genotypes[[3 ;; 4]]];
postsel[[1 ;; 2]] = Table[genotypes[[i]] / u, {i, 1, 2}];
postsel[[3 ;; 4]] = Table[((1 - st) * genotypes[[i]]) / u, {i, 3, 4}];

z = Total[postsel[[1 ;; 2]] * (c + (1 - c) * (1 / (at + 2))) +
Total[postsel[[3 ;; 4]] * (c + (1 - c) * ((at + 1) / (at + 2)))];

Mating = Table[Table[i, {i, 1, 4}], {j, 1, 4}];

Table[
Mating[[j, 1 ;; 4]] = Table[(genotypes[[j]] * postsel[[i]]), {i, 1, 4}], {j, {1, 3}}];

Table[Mating[[j, 1 ;; 2]] =
Table[(genotypes[[j]] * postsel[[i]] * (c + (1 - c) * (1 / (at + 2)))) / z, {i, 1, 2}], {j,
{2, 4}}];

Table[Mating[[j, 3 ;; 4]] =
Table[(genotypes[[j]] * postsel[[i]] * (c + (1 - c) * ((at + 1) / (at + 2)))) / z,
{i, 3, 4}], {j, {2, 4}}];

s = 0;
Do[
Do[
s = s + 1;
new[[s, 1 ;;]] = Mating[[h, k]] * recomb[[s, 1 ;;]], {k, 4}], {h, 4}];

genotypes[[1 ;; 4]] = Table[Total[new[[1 ;;, i]], {i, 4}];

(*once genotype frequencies are assigned, adjust due to biased mutation*)

mgenotypes = {1, 2, 3, 4, 5};
mgenotypes[[3 ;; 4]] = (1 - m) * genotypes[[3 ;; 4]];
mgenotypes[[1 ;; 2]] = m * genotypes[[3 ;; 4]] + genotypes[[1 ;; 2]];
mgenotypes[[5]] = mgenotypes[[1]] * mgenotypes[[4]] - mgenotypes[[2]] * mgenotypes[[3]];

genotypes = mgenotypes;

In[*]:= (*get the recursion equations*)
ΔT2 = Simplify[(genotypes[[3]] + genotypes[[4]] - T2];
ΔP2 = Simplify[(genotypes[[2]] + genotypes[[4]] - P2];
ΔLD = Simplify[genotypes[[5]] - DTP];

```

In[*]:= (*look at the expression for $\Delta T2$ when preference is fixed ($P2=1$ *)

$\Delta T2 = \text{FullSimplify}[\Delta T2 /. \{P2 \rightarrow 1, DTP \rightarrow 0\}]$

Out[*]:=
$$\frac{T2 \left(\text{at} \left(- (m+1) T2 (c+st-1) + cm + c - mst + m + st - 1 \right) - (c+1) (m(stT2 + st - 2) + st(T2 - 1)) \right)}{(2T2 \left(\text{at} (c+st-1) + cst + st \right) - 2 \left(\text{at} c + c + 1 \right))}$$

In[*]:= $\Delta T2_{noc} = \text{FullSimplify}[\Delta T2 /. \{P2 \rightarrow 1, DTP \rightarrow 0, c \rightarrow 0\}]$

Out[*]:=
$$\frac{T2 (2m + st - \text{at} (-1 + st) (-1 + m + T2 + mT2) - st (m + T2 + mT2))}{-2 + 2 (\text{at} (-1 + st) + st) T2}$$

(*Confirm that it is the same as Kirkpatrick 1982 with mutation bias when $c=0$ *)

In[*]:= $\text{Simplify}[-((T2(st(-1+T2) + a(-1+st)(-1+m+T2+mT2) + m(-2+st+stT2))) / (2(-1+a(-1+st)T2 + stT2))) = \Delta T2_{noc} /. \text{at} \rightarrow a]$

Out[*]:= True

(*Solve for Equilibria when $P2$ is fixed at 1*)

In[*]:= $\text{Simplify}[\Delta P2 /. \{P2 \rightarrow 1, DTP \rightarrow 0\}]$

Out[*]:= 0

In[*]:= $\text{Simplify}[\Delta LD /. \{P2 \rightarrow 1, DTP \rightarrow 0\}]$

Out[*]:= 0

In[*]:= $\text{Simplify}[\text{Solve}[\Delta T2 == 0, T2]]$

Out[*]:=
$$\left\{ \{T2 \rightarrow 0\}, \left\{ T2 \rightarrow \frac{-(1+c)(m(-2+st) - st) + \text{at}(-1+c+m+cm+st-mst)}{(1+m)((1+c)st + \text{at}(-1+c+st))} \right\} \right\}$$

In[*]:= $\text{Teq1} = \text{FullSimplify} \left[\frac{-(1+c)(m(-2+st) - st) + \text{at}(-1+c+m+cm+st-mst)}{(1+m)((1+c)st + \text{at}(-1+c+st))} \right]$

Out[*]:=
$$\frac{1 - m + \frac{2(1+c+at)c}{st+cm+at(-1+c+st)}}{1+m}$$

Test the stability of the equilibria by looking at the sign of the second derivative at the equilibrium points, given the constraints on the magnitudes of st , m , and c

In[*]:= $\text{sec1} = D[\Delta T2, T2] /. T2 \rightarrow \text{Teq1};$

$\text{sec0} = D[\Delta T2, T2] /. T2 \rightarrow 0;$

In[*]:= $\text{Reduce}[\text{sec1} < 0 \ \&\& \ 0 < m < 1 \ \&\& \ 0 < \text{at} \ \&\& \ 0 < st < 1 \ \&\& \ 0 < c < 1, \{\text{at}, c\}]$

Out[*]:=
$$0 < st < 1 \ \&\& \ 0 < m < 1 \ \&\& \ \text{at} > \frac{2m + st - mst}{1 - m - st + mst} \ \&\& \ 0 < c < \frac{\text{at} - 2m - \text{at}m - st - \text{at}st + mst + \text{at}mst}{\text{at} + 2m + \text{at}m + st - mst}$$

In[*]:= Reduce[sec0 < 0 && 0 < m < 1 && 0 < at && 0 < st < 1 && 0 < c < 1, {at, c}]

Out[*]:= $0 < st < 1 \&\& 0 < m < 1 \&\& \left(\left(0 < at \leq \frac{2m + st - mst}{1 - m - st + mst} \&\& 0 < c < 1 \right) \mid \mid \left(at > \frac{2m + st - mst}{1 - m - st + mst} \&\& \frac{at - 2m - at m - st - at st + mst + at mst}{at + 2m + at m + st - mst} < c < 1 \right) \right)$

In[*]:= FullSimplify $\left[\frac{2m + st - mst}{1 - m - st + mst}\right]$

Out[*]:= $-1 + \frac{1 + m}{(-1 + m)(-1 + st)}$

In[*]:= FullSimplify $\left[\frac{at - 2m - at m - st - at st + mst + at mst}{at + 2m + at m + st - mst}\right]$

Out[*]:= $\frac{at - 2m - at m + (1 + at)(-1 + m)st}{at + 2m + at m + st - mst}$

(*The T2=Teq equilibrium is stable as long as at >

$-1 + \frac{1+m}{(-1+m)(-1+st)}$ and $0 < c < \frac{at - 2m - at m + (1+at)(-1+m)st}{at + 2m + at m + st - mst}$.*)

In[*]:= Manipulate $\left[\left\{-1 + \frac{1 + m}{(-1 + m)(-1 + st)}, \frac{at - 2m - at m + (1 + at)(-1 + m)st}{at + 2m + at m + st - mst}\right\},\right.$

$\left.\left\{\{m, 0.1\}, 0, 1\}, \left\{\{st, 0.1\}, 0, 1\}, \left\{\{at, 4\}, -1 + \frac{1 + m}{(-1 + m)(-1 + st)}, 30\right\}\right\}\right]$

Demonstrate Stability Graphically

In[156]:= fΔT2[T2_, at_, st_, c_, m_] :=

$(T2 (at (-1 + c + m + c m + st - mst - (1 + m)(-1 + c + st) T2) - (1 + c)(st(-1 + T2) + m(-2 + st + st T2)))) / (-2(1 + c + at c) + 2(st + c st + at(-1 + c + st)) T2);$

```
In[157]:= Manipulate[Plot[fΔT2[T2, at, st, c, m], {T2, 0, 1}, PlotRange → Full],
  -1 +  $\frac{1+m}{(-1+m)(-1+st)}$ ,  $\frac{at-2m-atm+(1+at)(-1+m)st}{at+2m+atm+st-mst}$ },
  {{at, 8}, 0, 20}, {{c, 0.5}, 0, 1}, {{st, 0.1}, 0, 1}, {{m, 0.1}, 0, 1}]
```


Use the equilibrium condition to calculate the initial adjusted realized strength of female preference:

(*First, find the value of T_{eq} when $c=0$ *)

$$\text{In[*]:= } \frac{1 - m + \frac{2(1+c+at)c}{st+cst+at(-1+c+st)}m}{1+m} /. c \rightarrow 0$$

$$\text{Out[*]:= } \frac{1 - m + \frac{2m}{at(-1+st)+st}}{1+m}$$

(*Then we can ask what value of at in the case of $c=0$ would result in the same equilibrium value for T_2 with coercion in the system. This is the "operational" or "realized" magnitude of at *)

$$\text{In[*]:= } \text{Solve}\left[\frac{1 - m + \frac{2(1+c+at)c}{st+cst+at(-1+c+st)}m}{1+m} == \frac{1 - m + \frac{2m}{at_{real}(-1+st)+st}}{1+m}, at_{real}\right]$$

$$\text{Out[*]:= } \left\{ \left\{ at_{real} \rightarrow \frac{at - at c}{1 + c + at c} \right\} \right\}$$

$$\text{In[*]:= } \text{Factor}\left[\frac{at - at c}{1 + c + at c}\right]$$

$$\text{Out[*]:= } -\frac{at(c-1)}{atc+c+1}$$

(*We can plot the relationship between c and atreal:

atreal is always less than at. We can also see that the minimum value for atreal coincides with the maximum value for c for a stable initial non-zero T2 equilibrium (the x axis range limit) as well as with the minimum value for at (the orange line)*)

```
In[ ]:= Plot[{- $\frac{at(c-1)}{atc+c+1}$  /. at -> 12,  $-1 + \frac{1+m}{(-1+m)(-1+st)}$  /. {m -> 0.1, st -> 0.1}},
  {c, 0,  $\frac{at-2m-atm+(1+at)(-1+m)st}{at+2m+atm+st-mst}$  /. {at -> 12, m -> 0.1, st -> 0.1}},
  PlotRange -> {0, 12.5}]
```


Further, for the equilibrium condition, calculate the proportion of T2 males that females are able to mate with. Then evaluate at $c = 0$ to get the proportion of T2 males they would get if they had full sexual autonomy

```
In[ ]:= ClearAll[a, c, ab, m, st, Teq, Taut, initr2prop,
  T2, P2, DTP, ToPo, ToP, TPo, TP, T1P1, T1P2, T2P1, T2P2];
```

```
In[ ]:= T2 = Teq;
P2 = 1;
DTP = 0;
```

```
In[ ]:= init1 = Solve[{T1P1 + T1P2 + T2P1 + T2P2 == 1, T1P2 + T2P2 == P2,
  T2P1 + T2P2 == T2, DTP == T2P2 - T2 * P2}, {T1P1, T1P2, T2P1, T2P2}];
```

```
In[ ]:= T1P1 = T1P1 /. init1;
T1P2 = T1P2 /. init1;
T2P1 = T2P1 /. init1;
T2P2 = T2P2 /. init1;
```

```
In[ ]:= genotypes = Flatten[{T1P1, T1P2, T2P1, T2P2, (T1P1 * T2P2 - T1P2 * T2P1)}];
```

```
In[ ]:= genotypes
```

```
Out[ ]:= {0, 1 - Teq, 0, Teq, 0}
```

```
In[*]:= postsel = Table[i, {i, 1, 4}];
u = Total[genotypes[[1 ;; 2]] + (1 - st) * Total[genotypes[[3 ;; 4]]];
postsel[[1 ;; 2]] = Table[genotypes[[i]] / u, {i, 1, 2}];
postsel[[3 ;; 4]] = Table[((1 - st) * genotypes[[i]]) / u, {i, 3, 4}];
```

```
In[*]:= postsel
```

$$\text{Out[*]} = \left\{ 0, \frac{1 - \text{Teq}}{1 - \text{Teq} + (1 - \text{st}) \text{Teq}}, 0, \frac{(1 - \text{st}) \text{Teq}}{1 - \text{Teq} + (1 - \text{st}) \text{Teq}} \right\}$$

```
In[*]:= z = Total[postsel[[1 ;; 2]] * (c + (1 - c) * (1 / (at + 2))) +
Total[postsel[[3 ;; 4]] * (c + (1 - c) * ((at + 1) / (at + 2)))];
```

```
Mating = Table[Table[i, {i, 1, 4}], {j, 1, 4}];
```

```
Table[
```

```
Mating[[j, 1 ;; 4]] = Table[(genotypes[[j]] * postsel[[i]), {i, 1, 4}], {j, {1, 3}}];
```

```
Table[Mating[[j, 1 ;; 2]] =
```

```
Table[(genotypes[[j]] * postsel[[i]] * (c + (1 - c) * (1 / (at + 2)))) / z, {i, 1, 2}], {j,
{2, 4}}];
```

```
Table[Mating[[j, 3 ;; 4]] =
```

```
Table[(genotypes[[j]] * postsel[[i]] * (c + (1 - c) * ((at + 1) / (at + 2)))) / z,
{i, 3, 4}], {j, {2, 4}}];
```

(* male genotypes are the columns and female genotypes are the rows,
in the order T1P1, T1P2, T2P1, T2P2*)

```
MatrixForm[Mating]
```

```
Out[*]//MatrixForm=
```

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\left(\frac{1-c}{2+at}+c\right)(1-\text{Teq})^2}{(1-\text{Teq}+(1-\text{st})\text{Teq})\left(\frac{\left(\frac{1-c}{2+at}+c\right)(1-\text{Teq})}{1-\text{Teq}+(1-\text{st})\text{Teq}}+\frac{\left(\frac{(1+at)(1-c)}{2+at}+c\right)(1-\text{st})\text{Teq}}{1-\text{Teq}+(1-\text{st})\text{Teq}}\right)} & 0 & \frac{\left(\frac{(1+at)(1-c)}{2+at}+c\right)(1-\text{st})(1-\text{Teq})\text{Teq}}{(1-\text{Teq}+(1-\text{st})\text{Teq})\left(\frac{\left(\frac{1-c}{2+at}+c\right)(1-\text{Teq})}{1-\text{Teq}+(1-\text{st})\text{Teq}}+\frac{\left(\frac{(1+at)(1-c)}{2+at}+c\right)(1-\text{st})\text{Teq}}{1-\text{Teq}+(1-\text{st})\text{Teq}}\right)} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\left(\frac{1-c}{2+at}+c\right)(1-\text{Teq})\text{Teq}}{(1-\text{Teq}+(1-\text{st})\text{Teq})\left(\frac{\left(\frac{1-c}{2+at}+c\right)(1-\text{Teq})}{1-\text{Teq}+(1-\text{st})\text{Teq}}+\frac{\left(\frac{(1+at)(1-c)}{2+at}+c\right)(1-\text{st})\text{Teq}}{1-\text{Teq}+(1-\text{st})\text{Teq}}\right)} & 0 & \frac{\left(\frac{(1+at)(1-c)}{2+at}+c\right)(1-\text{st})\text{Teq}^2}{(1-\text{Teq}+(1-\text{st})\text{Teq})\left(\frac{\left(\frac{1-c}{2+at}+c\right)(1-\text{Teq})}{1-\text{Teq}+(1-\text{st})\text{Teq}}+\frac{\left(\frac{(1+at)(1-c)}{2+at}+c\right)(1-\text{st})\text{Teq}}{1-\text{Teq}+(1-\text{st})\text{Teq}}\right)} \end{pmatrix}$$

```
In[*]:= initr2prop = FullSimplify[(Mating[[2, 4]] + Mating[[4, 4]])]
```

$$\text{Out[*]} = \frac{(1 + at + c) (-1 + st) \text{Teq}}{-1 - (1 + at) c + (st + c st + at (-1 + c + st)) \text{Teq}}$$

```
In[*]:= (*proportion matings with T2 males with coercion*)
```

```
t2propeq = FullSimplify[initr2prop /. Teq -> Teq1]
```

$$\text{Out[*]} = 1 - \frac{2(1 + c + at c) m}{(-1 + m) (st + c st + at (-1 + c + st))}$$

(*calculate the proportion of T2 males a female gets when $c = 0$. This will be equal to the proportion of T2 males females gets when $\gamma=1$ and $B2=1*$)

In[*]:= `t2propaut = FullSimplify[t2propeq /. c -> 0]`

Out[*]:= $1 - \frac{2m}{(-1+m)(-1+st)+st}$